

Influence of various weed control treatments on weed control efficiency, growth, and yield of upland rice. Jabalpur, India.

Treatment ^a	Weed biomass (t/ha)	Effective tillers/plant	Crop biomass (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Treatment cost ^b (\$/ha)	Profit ^c (\$)
Thiobencarb 1.5 + 1 HW 30 DAS	0.2	2.7	13.7	9.3	4.4	93.45	241.46
Oxadiazon 0.75 + 1 HW 30 DAS	0.1	3.8	12.9	8.8	4.1	95.45	203.43
Pendimethalin 1 + 1 HW 30 DAS	0.2	3.0	11.6	7.5	4.1	90.00	195.10
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DAS	0.2	3.1	11.7	7.6	4.1	190.90	92.84
Oxadiazon 1.0	0.3	3.1	12.7	8.7	4.0	40.90	238.91
Thiobencarb 1.5	1.4	3.0	10.8	7.0	3.8	29.81	208.88
Oxadiazon 0.75	0.9	3.1	11.6	7.9	3.7	31.81	195.85
Thiobencarb 1.5 + 2,4-D EE 1.0	1.8	2.8	10.3	6.8	3.6	40.27	165.65
Hand hoeing 20 and 40 DAS	2.5	2.7	10.0	6.6	3.5	50.90	137.60
Thiobencarb 2.0	1.2	2.5	10.5	7.4	3.1	39.45	104.97
Pendimethalin 2.0	2.3	2.4	8.6	5.2	3.0	48.63	60.18
Pendimethalin 1.0 + 2,4-D EE 1.0	1.6	2.2	9.4	6.5	2.9	35.90	74.87
Weedy check	3.4	2.0	7.4	5.3	2.2	—	—
Pendimethalin 1.0	3.1	2.2	7.1	5.2	1.9	26.36	-64.94
CD at 5%	0.853	0.76	3.117	2.22	1.286		

^aHerbicide measurements are in kg ai/ha. HW = hand weeding. EE = ethyl ester. ^bCost of herbicide and labor: thiobencarb = \$1 7.45/liter, pendimethalin (G) = \$21.81/kg, oxadiazon = \$36.36/liter, 2,4-D EE = \$9.54/kg, application charges = \$4.54/ha, Cost of hand weeding 1 = \$127.27/ha, cost of hand weeding 2 = \$63.63/ha, cost of hoeing 1 = \$31.81/ha, cost of hoeing 2 = \$19.09/ha, hand weeding after herbicide application = \$63.36/ha, price of rice = \$136.3/t, and price of straw = \$8.18/t. ^cProfit = grain yield + straw yield minus treatment cost.

Weed control in hybrid rice

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We evaluated some herbicides to control weeds in hybrid rice Shen Zhan 97A/Saddang in the 1985-86 wet season. Herbicides were applied 3 d after transplanting.

The herbicides did not influence tillering and plant height. MCPA-K salt, oxadiazon, thiobencarb, and 2,4-D were not significantly different in controlling broadleaves, grasses, and sedges (see table). Piperophos + 2,4-D was not significantly different from hand weeding, especially for controlling grasses. Highest yield was with hand

Effect of some herbicides on tillering, plant height, weeds, and grain yield in hybrid rice. Maros, Indonesia, 1985-86 wet season.

Treatment	kg ai/ha	Tillers (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Dry weed ^a (g/m ²)			Grain yield (t/ha)
				Broad-leaves	Grasses	Sedges	
MCPA K salt	0.40	12	70	2.8 bc	2.0 b	1.2 bc	3.3 c
Oxadiazon	0.50	10	60	3.4 c	2.4 b	1.5 cd	3.4 c
Piperophos + 2,4-D	0.33 + 0.17	13	71	1.5 b	1.1 a	0.9 b	4.2 b
Thiobencarb	1.00	12	67	3.5 c	2.3 b	1.0 bc	3.2 cd
2,4-D	0.85	12	66	3.1 c	2.8 b	1.3 cd	3.4 c
Hand weeding 7 and 35 DT ^b		12	70	0.6 a	0.4 a	0.0 a	5.2 a
Unweeded control		10	70	8.9 d	5.1 c	2.9 d	2.3 d
CV (%)		20	7	16.4	21.5	23.6	12.0

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Data transformed to log (x + 1). ^bDays after transplanting.

weeding, then with piperophos + 2,4-D. Thiobencarb increased yield 35%. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Pomacea snails in the Philippines

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Pomacea snails indigenous to South America were recently introduced for human food in Taiwan (China), Japan, and the Philippines. Scientific names,

frequently confused, were determined by Habe as follows:

- Family: Pilidae (Ampullariidae)
- Pomacea canaliculata* (Lamarck)
- Ampullaria canaliculata*
- Ampullarium insularum* Hamada et Matsumoto 1985 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)

- Ampullarius insularus* Chang 1985 (nec d'orbigny 1839)
- Ampullarius insularus*. Miyazaki 1985 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)
- Ampullarius insularus* Miyahara et al. 1986 (nec d'Orbigny 1839)
- Pomacea gigas* (Spix)
- Ampullaria gigas*